

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

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2 **Figure 1.** Immune epigenome profiling of calves at birth (Day 0) **A.** Heatmap methylation
3 levels of differentially methylated cytosines (DMCs) used as markers to identify
4 methylation levels of blood among each calf. The transverse axis of the heatmap represents
5 each individual, with red representing calves that were exposed to prenatal heat stress and
6 blue representing calves that were not, and the longitudinal axis represents the 424 DMCs
7 used as markers across all chromosomes. Each lattice color in the heatmap represents a
8 level of methylation, with pale grey representing hypomethylated sites and dark grey
9 representing hypermethylated sites. **B.** Predicted blood cell fraction analysis of the seven
10 major immune cell types (B cell, CD4+, CD8+, and $\gamma\delta$ T cells, granulocytes, monocytes
11 and natural killers). Upper, midline and lower edge of the box represent the first quartile,
12 the median and the third quartile respectively, and whiskers and dots represent
13 minimum/maximum of the proportion of each blood cell type for each treatment and
14 individuals respectively. Red color represents calves that were exposed to prenatal heat
15 stress and blue color represents calves that were not. * represents P -adjusted < 0.05 and ns
16 represents P -adjusted > 0.05 between treatments.

18 **Figure 2.** Immune epigenome profiling of calves at weaning (Day 63) **A.** Heatmap
 19 methylation levels of differentially methylated cytosines (DMCs) used as markers to
 20 identify methylation levels of blood among each calf. The transverse axis of the heatmap
 21 represents each individual, with red representing calves that were exposed to prenatal heat
 22 stress and blue representing calves that were not, and the longitudinal axis represents the
 23 527 DMCs used as markers across all chromosomes. Each lattice color in the heatmap
 24 represents a level of methylation, with pale grey representing hypomethylated sites and
 25 dark grey representing hypermethylated sites. **B.** Predicted blood cell fraction analysis of
 26 the seven major immune cell types (B cell, CD4+, CD8+, and $\gamma\delta$ T cells, granulocytes,
 27 monocytes and natural killers). Upper, midline and lower edge of the box represent the first
 28 quartile, the median and the third quartile respectively, and whiskers and dots represent
 29 minimum/maximum of the proportion of each blood cell type for each treatment and
 30 individuals respectively. Red color represents calves that were exposed to prenatal heat
 31 stress and blue color represents calves that were not. ** represents *P-adjusted* < 0.01,
 32 *represents *P-adjusted* < 0.05 and ns represents *P-adjusted* > 0.05 between treatments.

